

MICROWAVE PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE CERAMIC PHASE SHIFTER MATERIALS

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Abstract

The microwave properties of bulk ceramic barium strontium titanate and non-ferroelectric oxide composites are measured at X-band with a cylindrical mode-filtered resonant cavity. A helical wire-wound waveguide makes up the cavity's cylindrical wall, which permits the use of high-purity TE_{01p} resonant modes for high accuracy permittivity measurements. Measurement results at 300K show that microwave dielectric losses increase as the stoichiometric percentage of barium increases. The real relative permittivity increases with decreasing weight percent of added non-ferroelectric low-loss oxide. Dielectric losses rapidly decrease with the addition of a relatively small amount of non-ferroelectric oxide.

1 Introduction

Recent advances in ceramic composites and thin-film deposition technologies have resulted in new ferroelectrics with voltage-tunable dielectric constants at room temperature and improved dielectric loss properties. These new ferroelectrics, whether in bulk or thin-film form, have potential uses in microwave circuit applications. One application is in phased-array antennas. These antennas are currently constructed using ferrite phase-shifting elements. The ferrite phase-shifting elements are relatively large and heavy. Because of the circuit requirements necessary to operate phased-array antennas, they are also expensive. Ferroelectric materials offer the promise of reduced size and weight, at a fraction of the cost. Therefore they could revolutionize phased-array an-

tennas and could make these devices available for many commercial uses. One figure of merit of phase-shifting elements is that of maximum, temperature-stable phase shift consistent with minimum insertion loss. In this paper we report microwave dielectric property measurements of various bulk composites of $Ba_xSr_{1-x}TiO_3$ and low-loss non-ferroelectric oxides. These properties can be directly related to insertion losses and can be used as tests of previous effective medium theory formulations for two-phase composites [1]. A very sensitive method was used to measure permittivity and dielectric loss tangent of disk samples. This method allows the accurate measurement of high permittivity materials whose dielectric loss tangents range from 10^{-5} to 10^{-2} .

2 Experimental Procedure

The 50-millimeter X-band mode-filtered cavity which was used to measure permittivity and dielectric loss tangent is shown in Fig. 1. The cavity is constructed with a helix waveguide to filter all modes resulting from current flow other than that flowing circumferentially about the cavity wall (Fig. 2). For a cylindrical cavity that is not mode-filtered, both TE_{01p} and interfering TM_{11p} modes occur, which results from both azimuthal and radial current flow in the cavity end plates and axial current flow in the cylinder wall (Fig. 3).

The use of helical guide yields a high-Q cavity with very pure TE-mode structure for precision electrical property measurements. No capacitive coupling between sample and cavity end plate occurs with TE_{01p} mode structure, and the quality factor for this mode

Figure 1: X-band mode-filtered cavity system.

Figure 2: TE_{01p} mode filter consisting of helically-wound waveguide.

Figure 3: Currents flowing in (a) cylinder wall and (b) cavity end plates for TE_{01p} and TM_{11p} modes.

structure in a resonant cavity is highest for most useful cylindrical cavity geometries. Repeatable measurements may therefore be performed that are not affected by depolarization problems frequently encountered in low-frequency capacitive fixtures or with the use of TM-modes. Non- TE_{01p} modes, if excited in the mode-filtered cavity, are attenuated by at least 30 dB. Adjustable coupling loops are also used so that external losses are negligible. Details of cylindrical mode-filtered cavities have been treated elsewhere [2-4] and will not be further discussed here.

The nonzero field components interior to a right circular cylindrical cavity for TE_{01p} mode structure are well known [2]. The axial magnetic field is

$$H_z = H_0 J_0\left(\frac{t'_{01}r}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{p\pi z}{L}\right), \quad (1)$$

where J_0 is the Bessel function of zero order, a is the cavity radius, L is the length of the cavity at resonance, and $t'_{01} \approx 3.8317$ is the first zero of J_0 . The two other nonzero field components are derivable from H_z using Maxwell's equations expanded in cylindrical coordinates:

$$H_r = \frac{1}{k_c^2} \frac{\partial^2 H_z}{\partial z \partial r} = \frac{pH_0\pi a}{t'_{01}L} J'_0\left(\frac{t'_{01}r}{a}\right) \cos\left(\frac{p\pi z}{L}\right), \quad (2)$$

$$E_\phi = \frac{j\omega\mu_0}{k_c^2} \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial r} = \frac{j\omega\mu_0 H_0 a}{t'_{01}} J'_0\left(\frac{t'_{01}r}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{p\pi z}{L}\right). \quad (3)$$

Application of boundary conditions at resonance for the tangential electric and magnetic fields on the surface on a homogeneous, linear, isotropic dielectric disk sample and for the tangential electric field on the

cavity end plates yields the following transcendental equation in terms of the axial wavenumber β_1 in the sample under test,

$$\frac{\tan(\beta_1 b)}{\beta_1} = -\frac{\tan[\beta_0(L-b)]}{\beta_0}, \quad (4)$$

where $\beta_1 = \sqrt{\omega^2 \epsilon_r' \mu_0 \epsilon_0 - k_c^2}$, $\beta_0 = \sqrt{(\omega/c_{air})^2 - k_c^2}$, $k_c = t'_{01}/a$, c_{air} is the speed of light in air, and μ_0 and ϵ_0 are free space permeability, $4\pi \times 10^{-7}$ H/m and permittivity, $8.854 187 \times 10^{-12}$ F/m, b is sample thickness, ω is radian frequency, and ϵ_r' is the relative real permittivity of the sample under test. Equation (4) may be solved numerically for β_1 , from which the relative real permittivity is given by

$$\epsilon_r' = \frac{\beta_1^2 + k_c^2}{\beta_0^2 + k_c^2}. \quad (5)$$

Since no radiative losses occur, the dielectric loss tangent is evaluated from

$$\tan \delta = p_e^{-1} (1/Q_u - 1/Q_c), \quad (6)$$

where p_e is the electric-energy filling factor, Q_u is the unloaded quality factor with dielectric sample, and Q_c^{-1} is the conductor loss. The empty cavity quality factor Q_c for TE_{01p} mode structure is given by

$$Q_c = \frac{\eta}{2} \frac{\left[\left(\frac{t'_{01}}{a} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{p\pi}{L} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\frac{R_{m,side}}{a} \left(\frac{t'_{01}}{a} \right)^2 + \frac{2R_{m,ep}}{L} \left(\frac{p\pi}{L} \right)^2}, \quad (7)$$

where $\eta = \sqrt{\mu_0/\epsilon'_{air}}$, and $R_{m,side}$ and $R_{m,ep}$ are the measured surface resistances of the helical cavity sidewall and copper end plates. The surface resistance of the endplates are measured using a sapphire rod as a dielectric resonator whose aspect ratio allowed TE₀₁₁ resonance at 10 GHz [5]. For any other measured frequency, this surface resistance is determined by assuming a $f^{1/2}$ frequency dependence. The cavity helical sidewall surface resistance is then calculated by measuring the (empty) unloaded Q -factor.

3 Results

Dielectric measurements of some ceramic phase shifter composite materials with added non-ferroelectric oxide are summarized in Table I. These results were obtained with the fixed-frequency technique using the TE₀₁₃ mode. The influence of barium content in the Ba_xSr_{1-x}TiO₃ phase of the composite on measured dielectric properties is shown in Fig. 4. A much more rapid change in dielectric loss than change in real permittivity is observed with increasing barium content. The measurements were performed at 300K, far from the Curie transition temperature. Losses generally decrease with the addition of a

Figure 4: Relative real permittivity and dielectric loss as a function of barium content in the Ba_xSr_{1-x}TiO₃ phase of the composite.

non-ferroelectric low-loss oxide phase in the composite. This decrease in dielectric loss is relatively rapid with a small additive non-ferroelectric oxide phase, and then changes more slowly with additional non-ferroelectric oxide in the composite.

A detailed uncertainty analysis which includes sources of measurement uncertainty due to cavity and dielectric sample dimensions, cavity conductor losses, and determination of resonance frequency and Q factor was also performed. Systematic uncertainties in the determination of ϵ_r' are only weakly affected by capacitive coupling to the cavity end plate, disassembly of the cavity, or by imperfections of the dielectric sample faces, since for TE_{01p} modes the electric field has only an azimuthal component tangential and contiguous with the sample surface. The interfering effects of higher-order resonant TE modes observed with high-permittivity sample insertion are mitigated with specimen thicknesses less than one-half guide wavelength at the measurement frequency. Typical total uncertainty for well-machined samples of these high-permittivity ceramic composites is ± 1.0 percent for ϵ_r' , which is primarily due to dimensional uncertainties. Loss tangent uncertainties depend on the accuracy with which the cavity conductor losses and unloaded Q factor are determined, as well as the partial electric-energy filling factor. The maximum total uncertainty in loss tangent determination is estimated to be $\pm 3 \times 10^{-5}$.

Table 1: MICROWAVE DIELECTRIC PROPERTY MEASUREMENTS ON FERROELECTRIC CERAMIC COMPOSITES AT 10 GHZ.

Material	Weight Percent, Added Oxide	Curie Temperature °C	Relative Permittivity	Loss Tangent
Ba _{0.50} Sr _{0.50} TiO ₃	0	-25	1099	1.80 × 10 ⁻²
Ba _{0.50} Sr _{0.50} TiO ₃	20	-55	616	8.67 × 10 ⁻³
Ba _{0.50} Sr _{0.50} TiO ₃	30	-50	463	8.45 × 10 ⁻³
Ba _{0.50} Sr _{0.50} TiO ₃	60	-45	84.5	6.55 × 10 ⁻³
Ba _{0.55} Sr _{0.45} TiO ₃	30	-45	527	1.21 × 10 ⁻²
Ba _{0.55} Sr _{0.45} TiO ₃	60	-50	99.8	7.95 × 10 ⁻³
Ba _{0.60} Sr _{0.40} TiO ₃	60	-55	118	1.29 × 10 ⁻²

4 Summary

The use of a TE_{01p} mode-filtered cavity permits very accurate microwave dielectric property measurements on high permittivity ferroelectric ceramic composites. These measurements allow the optimization of phase-shifting components in phased-antenna arrays which incorporate these materials. As the stoichiometric ratio of Ba/Sr in Ba_xSr_{1-x}TiO₃ phase of the composite increases, dielectric losses rapidly increase. Addition of non-ferroelectric oxides can be used to control the effective real permittivity and dielectric loss of the composite.

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6 References

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